

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PERCEPTION ON JOB SATISFACTION AMONG POLICE OFFICERS: BASIS FOR AN IMPROVED PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Police officers' work-life conflict is linked to more subjective health complaints, suicidal thoughts, burnout, and stress in addition to higher degrees of job discontent. Further research findings highlight the significant relationship between stress and work-life balance or work-family conflict affecting police officers regardless of their gender, despite the fact that significant gender differences regarding psychosocial stress were found in general, but especially among police officers who were married and/or had children. Similarly, despite conflicting findings, several research show that gender neither predicts nor significantly differs between male and female police officers in terms of job satisfaction.

This study was focused on determining the factors influencing the perception of job satisfaction among police officers which will be used as a basis for improved personnel management in terms of environment and atmosphere, compensation, standards and policies, people, leadership, and organization. This study was participated by one hundred sixty police officers (160). This study was focused on determining the factors influencing the perception of job satisfaction among police officers which will be used as a basis for improved personnel management in terms of environment and atmosphere, compensation, standards and policies, people, leadership, and organization. This study used a purposive sampling technique in choosing the respondents of this study. The descriptive design is an appropriate method to facilitate the gathering of reliable and accurate data through research and conduct of the survey measurement of two or more variables to determine or estimate the extent to which the values for the variables are related or change in an identifiable pattern.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, psychosocial stress, personnel management, environment and atmosphere, compensation, standards and policies, people, leadership and organization*

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INTRODUCTION

Although the idea of job satisfaction has been well studied in other professions, there hasn't been much empirical research on job satisfaction among police officers. Increases in intrinsic workplace conditions result in increased levels of employee satisfaction and motivation.

Shift work is unavoidably one of the many work-related obligations that police officers must deal with on the job. Working in shifts, especially at night, is linked to a number of health hazards, including an increased risk of cancer due to reduced melatonin secretion and greater occurrences of cardiovascular diseases caused by a disrupted circadian rhythm (WHO, 2019). Additionally, alternating shift work is linked to an increased risk of sleep disruptions, poor mood and performance, and strained social and familial ties, all of which can be detrimental to one's physical and mental health. Balancing work and leisure activities, such as partnership, family, caring for relatives, hobbies or voluntary work, thus poses a particular challenge for employees working in alternating shifts. Similarly, job satisfaction is closely related to both physical and mental health.

Prior study in the global context has concentrated on the quality of their sleep, work-related stress(ors), trauma, and linked suicidal ideation, particularly among shift-working police officers. Comparing the risk of suicide to other occupational groupings, it is noticeably greater. However, the perceived stress that police officers experience at work is a product of both their working environment and the work they conduct. For instance, longer than 11-hour hours, required overtime, and erratic scheduling have all been linked to an increased risk of burnout in police officers. Shift work is a need for police officers, and it predicts work-family conflict and illness absence. The latter also acts as a mediator between workplace stress and job satisfaction among police personnel and their workload.

A lack of consistency exists in the literature's conclusions about the gender and perceived quality of life of police personnel. Arroyo et. al. (2019) indicates that while total scores between male and female police officers do not significantly differ, female police officers reported lower levels on certain subscales of health-related quality of life, which, like work satisfaction, is inversely correlated with felt stress. Significant interactions weren't found, though. Other research has not discovered any appreciable gender variations in police officers' quality of life. The study of police officers' quality of life, however, is still in its infancy.

Law enforcement is a system wherein some people in a society work together in an organized way to uphold the law by identifying, discouraging, rehabilitating, or punishing those who disobey the laws and standards that govern that particular society. The people who personally engage in patrols or surveillance to deter and uncover criminal conduct, as well as those who investigate crimes and catch offenders—a role normally performed by the police—are the ones who use it most frequently. The Philippine National Police is in charge of enforcing the law in the Philippines (PNP). The Constitution of the Revolutionary Government was reportedly used to create the first police organization in the Philippines during the administration of Emilio Aguinaldo (Gonzales, 2020).

Given that law enforcement is carried out by individuals, it follows that all law enforcers must be happy in their jobs in order to do their jobs successfully. The satisfaction levels of police officers, who are also employees, are proven to be factors that are closely related to an employee's performance.

There were no comparable studies on the satisfaction levels of law enforcement personnel worldwide as of the time of writing. However, a ranking of the top-performing police organizations offers information because there is evidence linking performance with employee happiness. The California Highway Patrol of the United States, the Royal Canadian Mounted Police of Canada, the Metropolitan Police Service of England, the Australian Federal Police, the New

York Police Department, The People's Armed Forces of China, the New Zealand Police, the Federal Police of Austria, the Garda Sochána of Ireland, and ranked first is the Icelandic Police of Iceland, according to a report by Infotainworld (2016).

Numerous studies on the levels of job satisfaction of police personnel have been conducted in the Philippines, taking into account diverse jurisdictions. They all come to the same conclusion: the police officers were content, especially a study by Bantang et al (2018) discovered that the Manila Police District officers were happy with their jobs. The level of job satisfaction of police officers has not yet been studied.

The term "job satisfaction" has many definitions. The most accurate definition, nevertheless, is "a pleasurable or positive emotional state coming from the appraisal of one's employment or job experiences" (Judge & Klinger, 2018). There are several variables that affect job happiness. These variables include pay and benefits for employees, working environment, the nature of the task itself, relationships at work, corporate rules, employee evaluation and recognition, and several other variables.

The researcher pursues the completion of this study in order to obtain and share information regarding the job satisfaction of police officers in Manila Police District in response to the dearth of research regarding PNP commissioned officers' job satisfaction as well as the non-commissioned.

Objectives

This study was focused on the factors influencing the perception on job satisfaction among police officers which will be used as a basis for improved personnel management.

Specifically, the researcher answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. position;
 - 1.4. civil status; and
 - 1.5. number of years in service
2. What is the level of job satisfaction as perceived by police officers themselves in PNP in terms of:
 - 2.1. environment and atmosphere;
 - 2.2. compensation;
 - 2.3. standards and policies;
 - 2.4. people;
 - 2.5. leadership and organization
3. Is there a significant difference between the assessments of the respondents on the level of job satisfaction when grouped according to profile?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations may be proposed for an improved personnel management?

METHODS

Research Design

In this study, the researcher used the descriptive-quantitative method of research. Descriptive research, also known as statistical research, describes data and characteristics of the population of phenomena being studied. Descriptive research answers the questions of who, what, where, when, and how. It will be concerned with condition relationships that exist, practices that prevail, beliefs, and processes that are developing. This research will be defined for the purpose of processing gathered data, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs processes, trends, and cause-effect relationships, and then making adequate interpretations about such data with or without the aid of statistical methods. The purpose of employing the descriptive method is to describe the nature of a condition, as it takes place during the time of the study, and to explore the cause or causes of a particular condition. The researcher opted to use this kind of research considering the desire to acquire first-hand data from the respondents so as to formulate rational and sound conclusions and recommendations for the study.

Population and Sampling

This study was participated by one hundred sixty police officers (160). In addition, the researcher used the purposive sampling technique as the sampling design. As defined by Easton & McColl, purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling) is a sampling technique in which a researcher relies on his or her own judgment when choosing members of a population to participate in the study. In Pandemic time, it is difficult to gather respondents. This is the reason that the researcher associated the incidental sampling techniques in determining the actual number of samples.

According to Creswell (1994), the descriptive method of research is to gather information about the present existing condition. Since the study is focused on the level of job satisfaction as perceived by police officers themselves in PNP, the descriptive method is the most appropriate method to use. The researcher used simple random sampling in order to achieve the target sample for data gathering.

Instrumentation

The easiest and fastest way of gathering information is through questionnaires. According to Calderon and Gonzales (1993), a questionnaire is a set of questions which, when answered properly by a required number of properly selected respondents, will supply the necessary information to complete a research study.

The questionnaire will be made and designed simply by the researcher so that most of the respondents will be able to answer the question by placing a mark of check on the appropriate space provided on the questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into 3 parts.

The First Part determined the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status position, and number of years in service.

Second Part identified the level of job satisfaction as perceived by police officers themselves in PNP in terms of job characteristics, supervisors, policies and programs, career and development, placement and promotion and grievance mechanism.

For the validation of the questionnaire, a group of three experts reviewed its content and all their suggestions were incorporated for the adequacy and reliability of the research instrument.

Data Collection

The following steps were taken into consideration in gathering data necessary to achieve the objective of the study: Permission to conduct the study was prepared by the researcher. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire and the certified evaluators were asked to answer the said questionnaire honestly. The respondents are assured that their responses are truly confidential and intended only to the study.

The researcher conducted and distributed the survey questionnaires to the respondents for them to answer.

After the completion of the questionnaire, each item was analyzed separately or in some cases, item responses may be summed to create a score for a group of items. Hence, Likert scales are often called summative scales (Trochim, 2006).

Data collected were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

The following statistical measures were employed to analyze the data:

Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents as well as the problems encountered by the respondents that affect their job satisfaction.

The Weighted mean was used to measure the general response of the survey samples, whether they agreed to a given statement or not.

Four-point scale was used to interpret items in the questionnaire. These responses were based on the level of job satisfaction as perceived by police officers themselves in PNP.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age

Category	Frequency	Percent
20-30 years old	21	13.0
31-40 years old	54	34.0
41-50 years old	80	50.0
51 and above	5	3.0
Total	160	100.0

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of age. Majority (f=54, 34.0 percent) of the respondents are 31-40 years old, followed by 20-30 years old (f=21, 21.0 percent), 41-50 years old (f=80, 50.0 percent), and 51 and above (f=5, 5.0 percent). These results suggest that most of the surveyed police officers are middle-aged.

Table 2

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Category	Frequency	Percent
Male	99	62.0
Female	61	38.0
Total	160	100.0

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of sex. Most (f=99, 62.0 percent) of the respondents are male followed by sixty-one (61) female respondents or 38.0 percent of the total surveyed sample. This is a male-dominated study.

Table 3

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Category	Frequency	Percent
Single	77	48.0
Married	83	52.0
Separated	0	0.0
Widow/Widower	0	0.0
Total	160	100.0

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of civil status. Majority (f=83, 52.0 percent) of the respondents are married followed by single (f=77, 48.0 percent) and no respondents who are separated and widow/widower.

Table 4

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Position

Category	Frequency	Percent
Police Commissioned	55	34.0
Police Non-Commissioned	105	66.0
Total	160	100.0

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of position. Majority (f=105, 66.0 percent) of the respondents are Police Non-Commissioned followed by Police Commissioned (f=55, 34.0 percent).

Table 5

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Number of Years in Service

Category	Frequency	Percent
Less than 5 years	27	17.0
5-10 years	40	25.0
11-15 years	51	32.0
16-20 years	32	20.0
21 years and above	10	6.0
Total	160	100.0

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of number of years in service. Most (f=51, 32.0 percent) of the surveyed police officers have been in the service for 11-15 years, followed by 5-10 years (f=40, 25.0 percent), 16-20 years (f=32, 20.0 percent), less than 5 years (f=27, 17.0 percent), and 21 years and above (f=10, 6.0 percent).

Table 6

Level of Job Satisfaction as Perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of Environment and Atmosphere

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Satisfied with the culture of the workplace	3.10	Agree
Contributed a lot in during the job well	3.27	Strongly Agree
Workplace is conducive to assigned task	3.57	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.31	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A); 1.75 – 2.49; Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.74-Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 6 shows the level of job satisfaction as perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of environment and atmosphere with a composite mean of 3.31 and is interpreted as strongly agree.

In terms of environment and atmosphere, respondents strongly agreed that the workplace is conducive to assigned tasks ($x=3.57$) and they are convinced that it contributed a lot to executing their job well ($x=3.27$) and only agreed that it satisfies the culture in the workplace ($x=3.10$).

Based on the results, it can be said that environment and atmosphere contribute to the organizational culture which is a set of shared values, beliefs, and norms that influence how employees think, feel, and behave in the workplace. Organizational culture serves four purposes: it instills a sense of belonging in participants, increases their commitment, supports organizational principles, and operates as a behavioral control mechanism.

Organizational culture encourages the appropriate solution to know the issues, which members learn, feel, and set the values, standards, actions, trends, and norms that promote high levels of achievement (Marcoulides & Heck, 1993; Schein, 1992). Quality is a wider indicator that may include reliability, performance, quality, and so on. On the other hand, performance metrics may include outcomes, habits and relative measures, principles, and tools for education and training, including management development and leadership training to construct appropriate performance management skills and attitudes (Richard, 2002).

Table 7

Level of Job Satisfaction as Perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of Compensation

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Compensated fairly	3.66	Strongly Agree
Well defined policies in salary and wages	3.48	Strongly Agree
Fair practice in promotion and provision of training	3.08	Agree
Composite Mean	3.41	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A); 1.75 – 2.49; Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.74-Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 7 presents the level of job satisfaction as perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of compensation with a composite mean of 3.41 and is interpreted as strongly agree.

In terms of compensation, the majority of the respondents strongly agreed that they are compensated fairly ($x=3.66$) and that policies about salary and wages are well-defined ($x=3.48$). Further, a handful of respondents agreed

that there is a fair practice in the promotion and provision of training ($x=3.08$). These results can be associated to the fact that employees are more motivated to come to work when they are well compensated. Their morale remains high, and they are more satisfied with their jobs. Employee morale is high when they are motivated to come to work every day and do their jobs to the best of their abilities.

These results are attested by the study conducted by Kotler in 2012. He argued that organizational culture has the power to increase organizational performance, employee job satisfaction, and a sense of certainty about problem solving. If an organizational culture is aligned with the evolving demands of internal and/or external stakeholders, the efficacy of the company will decrease, as has happened with some organizations (Ernst, 2011). Clearly, organizational culture and success are related (Kopelman, Brief, & Guzzo, 2011), although there is mixed evidence about the exact existence of this relationship. Analysis indicates that the association between many cultural characteristics and high performance over time has not been reliable (Denison, 2011; Sorenson, 2011).

Table 8

Level of Job Satisfaction as Perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of Standards and Policies

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The policy or procedure of company is clear and easy to understand	3.01	Agree
Policy well aligned with the mission and vision of the company	3.15	Agree
Employee's manual and handbook can be accessed easily	3.26	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.14	Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A); 1.75 – 2.49; Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.74-Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 8 shows the level of job satisfaction as perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of standards and policies with a composite mean of 3.14 and is interpreted as strongly agree.

Respondents strongly agreed that the employee's manual and handbook can be accessed easily ($x=3.26$) and some agreed that the policy or procedure of the company is clear and easy to understand ($x=3.01$) and are well-aligned with the mission and vision of the company ($x=3.15$). The results give credence that any organization's policies and processes are crucial. Policies and procedures work together to produce a road map for day-to-day operations. They guarantee that laws and regulations are followed, that decision-making is guided, and that internal processes are streamlined.

The idea of "culture" is also associated with myths, rituals, foreign languages and traditions, with strange, remote cultures and locations. Researchers have found that members of organizations similarly participate in rituals within our own community, pass on corporate myths and stories, and use arcane language, and that these informal activities may encourage or impede the organization's objective of management (Baker, 2011). A variety of concepts have been proposed for organizational culture in the organizational behavior literature. For instance, organizational culture was described by Kilmann et al. (1985) as "the shared philosophies, ideologies, values, assumptions, beliefs, expectations, attitudes and norms" that unite an organization. Deal (1986) defined it as "the human innovation that generates unity and significance and encourages devotion and productivity." Uttal (1983) defined it as a "system of common principles (what is important) and beliefs (how things work) that communicate with the individuals, organizational structures, and control systems of a business to produce behavioral standards.

Table 9

Level of Job Satisfaction as Perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of People

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Regularly take time to figure out ways to improve team’s work	3.18	Agree
Workers have the skills and expertise their jobs well	3.09	Agree
Workers are committed to do quality work	3.11	Agree
Composite Mean	3.13	Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A); 1.75 – 2.49; Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.74-Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 9 presents the level of job satisfaction as perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of people with a composite mean of 3.13 and is interpreted as agree.

In terms of people, the majority of the police respondents agreed that they regularly take time to figure out ways to improve the team’s work ($x=3.18$) and workers are committed to doing quality work ($x=3.11$) with skills and expertise their jobs well ($x=3.09$). Employees might be regarded to be an organization's genuine assets based on the findings. They are the people who make a significant contribution to an organization's success. They put up a great effort to offer their best work and meet the specified goals within the time range.

Some scholars have simply defined culture as "a system of informal rules that explain how people act most of the time" (Deal & Kennedy, 1982). Schein (1992) provided a generally accepted concept of organizational culture as a pattern of fundamental assumptions conceived, discovered, or formed by a given community as it learns to deal with the problem of external adaptation and internal integration, which has worked well enough to be considered true. In addition, culture may also be seen as consisting of three stages, with actions and objects being the most visible level (Schein, 1992). In an organization, these aspects of culture are easier to observe and include more straightforward member behavior trends and aspects of culture than others (e.g., work environment layout, technology, dress codes, building decorum).

Table 10

Level of Job Satisfaction as Perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of Leadership

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Manager makes the workers as a part of a team	3.27	Strongly Agree
Manager gives a clear instruction in a given task	3.39	Strongly Agree
Manager takes an interest in professional development	3.51	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.39	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A); 1.75 – 2.49; Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.74-Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 10 shows the level of job satisfaction as perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of leadership with a composite mean of 3.39 and is interpreted as strongly agree.

Based on the leadership assessment of the respondents, it can be seen that most of the respondents highly agreed that their superiors give clear instruction in a given task ($x=3.51$) and provide clear instruction in a given task ($x=3.39$) as well as make the workers as a part of a team ($x=3.27$). Indeed, leadership is a critical management function that enables an organization's resources be directed for increased efficiency and goal achievement. Effective leaders clarify the organization's mission, motivate employees, and assist them to achieve it.

Adoptive cultural and accomplishment orientations directly influence results. Humanistic orientation and Transformational Leadership through achievement orientation have had an indirect and positive effect on organizational results. Constructive cultural styles have had a positive effect on both organizational and individual performance generators, and dysfunctional defensive styles have had a negative impact. The link between corporate culture and productivity appears to be strong and consistent. There is a weak and indirect connection between internal cultures and performance. There are direct, strong, and positive links between innovative and competitive culture with organizational performance (Ogbonna and Harris, 2014). The presence of cultural traits of mission, adaptability, involvement, and consistency are positively related to performance perceptions. The presence of cultural traits of adhocracy, clan, hierarchy, or market is very much related to organizational effectiveness (Cameron and Freeman, 2015). Strong shared values can increase organizational performance (Deal and Kennedy (2014).

Table 11

Level of Job Satisfaction as Perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of Organization

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
There is an opportunity for individual career growth and development within the company	3.09	Agree
The organization provides a conducive work are for its employees	3.22	Agree
The company is not obligating its employees to render overtime it respects family time	3.51	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.27	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA); 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A); 1.75 – 2.49; Disagree (D); 1.00 – 1.74-Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 11 exhibits the level of job satisfaction as perceived by Police Officers themselves in PNP in terms of organization with a composite mean of 3.27 and is interpreted as strongly agree.

In terms of organizational variable, most of the respondents strongly agreed that the company is not obligating its employees to render overtime it respects family time ($x=3.51$) and agreed that the organization is providing a conducive work are for its employees ($x=3.22$) as well as an opportunity for individual career growth and development within the company ($x=3.09$). Based on the results, respondents can save time looking for things and have more time to work on vital activities if they stay organized. They can make their team more productive by improving the flow of communication between them and the team through structure. Better communication, after all, leads to better outcomes.

Variables of Job satisfaction viz. professionalism, control and interaction are strongly related with commitment (Lok and Crawford, 1999). Innovation is defined as the process of turning a new concept into a product or service that generates value for others. Cultural considerations and the organization's dedication to a welcoming atmosphere, a constraint-free environment, research and development, strategic direction, a technically sound team and sufficient funding are linked. The relation between the need for achievement & creativity is moderated by innovative Culture, whereas relation between the need for power and creativity is moderated by traditional culture. The relation between the need for affiliation and creativity is moderated by cooperative culture (Hon and Leung, 2011).

Table 12

Significant Difference between the Assessments of the Respondents on the Level of Job Satisfaction when grouped according to Profile

	F-value	Sig. value	Decision	Remarks
Environment and Atmosphere	3.121	.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Compensation	2.552	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Standards and Policies	1.001	.002	Reject Ho	Significant
People	2.112	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Leadership	2.001	.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Organization	1.752	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 12 shows the significant difference between the assessments of the respondents on the level of job satisfaction when grouped according to profile. The computed Sig. values for environment and atmosphere (.001), compensation (.000), standards and policies (.002), people (.000), leadership (.000), and organization (.000) rejected the null hypothesis of no significant difference. This means that the level of satisfaction of police personnel and their profile are significantly different.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that most of the respondents are young entrepreneurs and this study is a female-dominated study. Given their profile, respondents are focused on running the business and are just starting the company. It may be inferred that the organizational culture, which is a set of shared values, beliefs, and standards that impact how employees think, feel, and behave in the workplace, is influenced by the surroundings and atmosphere. Organizational culture serves four purposes: it gives individuals a sense of belonging, boosts their commitment, reinforces organizational ideals, and acts as a behavioral control mechanism. These findings can be linked to the fact that employees who are well compensated are more motivated to come to work. Their spirits are still high, and they are happier in their occupations. When employees are motivated to come to work every day and accomplish their jobs to the best of their abilities, employee morale is strong.

The findings demonstrated the importance of policies and processes in any company. Policies and procedures are used in tandem to create a road map for day-to-day operations. They ensure that laws and regulations are obeyed, decisions are led, and internal procedures are streamlined. Based on the findings, employees may be considered true assets of a firm. They are the individuals who make a substantial contribution to the success of an organization. They put up significant effort to provide their best job and achieve the stated deadlines. Indeed, leadership is a crucial management role that allows an organization's resources to be directed for greater efficiency and goal attainment. Effective leaders make the objective of the company clear, motivate employees, and help them achieve it. According to the findings, staying organized allows respondents to spend less time seeking things and more time working on important tasks. They can increase the productivity of their team by enhancing the flow of communication between them and the rest of the team. After all, better communication leads to better results.

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